

Computational Modeling of Diachronic Variation in Late and Medieval Latin

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The following proposal is intended for an “oral presentation” of an ongoing research project (PhD thesis).

This research, situated within the field of computational philology, aims to develop a model for automatically dating Latin texts based exclusively on linguistic features. Although stylometric methods are firmly established for authorship attribution [3, 5, 9, 10, 13, 14, 16], their application to temporal classification has received little attention. Previous studies [6, 15, 18] suggest that diachronic linguistic variation can be quantified and leveraged for chronological attribution. Building on this premise, the present work applies this principle to a large corpus of Late and Medieval Latin texts, in a context where such methods remain uncommon. Beyond its practical utility for dating, this approach provides new insights into the mechanisms of linguistic change over nearly a millennium.

The corpus at the heart of this project consists of Latin hagiographic texts, written between Late Antiquity and the Middle Ages. These writings are literary works in their own right, and this nature introduces major challenges for computational analysis. Many are anonymous, frequently rewritten across centuries, and heavily intertextual, including frequent unmarked biblical quotations [1, 4, 7, 8]. Furthermore, Latin itself underwent profound sociolinguistic changes during this period. Initially a native language, it gradually evolved into the Romance languages and, following the Carolingian reform, became a learned language no longer acquired as a mother tongue [2, 11, 12, 17]. Such overlapping phenomena (i.e. textual transmission, intertextuality, and linguistic evolution) blur chronological markers and complicate the identification of temporal features.

To address these complexities, a distinction is made between two corpora: a restricted corpus of all the hagiographic texts edited in the *Patrologia Latina*, and an extended corpus encompassing a broader range of Late and Medieval Latin literature, drawn mainly (but not exclusively) from the same *Patrologia Latina*. This extended corpus currently contains over 5,000 texts and offers greater diversity across the centuries, making it an essential foundation for building and testing the model. As a first stage, the analysis concentrates on this extended corpus to identify robust chronological features

and reliable classification methods before progressing to the more intricate and ambiguous hagiographic material. This phased approach ensures that the model is developed on solid ground before tackling the specific challenges posed by hagiography.

Within this first stage, the initial step consists of a simplified task: distinguishing between two distant chronological windows (4th-5th centuries and 11th-12th centuries) regardless of literary genre. Texts were chosen to ensure that both periods are represented by a similar number of tokens, allowing for fair comparison. This choice maximizes temporal separation and provides a clear test case for detecting diachronic signals. Texts are lemmatized and part-of-speech (POS) tagged, with non-informative elements such as punctuation removed. The decision to focus on POS bigrams stems from the need to capture syntactic tendencies rather than lexical content, which can be heavily influenced by genre or topic. POS bigrams provide a compact representation of grammatical patterns that tend to evolve over time and thus serve as potential chronological markers. Frequencies are computed over 500-word segments to increase sample size and account for internal variation within texts. In this prototype, 49 POS bigrams form the feature set, normalized across segments to ensure comparability.

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier with a linear kernel was trained on two-thirds of the data and tested on the remaining third. The model achieves an accuracy of 86.9%, compared to a 50% baseline for random guessing. Texts from the 4th–5th centuries are correctly classified in 89% of cases, and those from the 11th–12th centuries in 85% (see Table 1). These results suggest that diachronic signals can be detected through shallow syntactic features alone, even without lexical or semantic information. This finding is significant because it demonstrates that structural tendencies do carry strong chronological information.

		Actual	
		4th–5th c.	11th–12th c.
Predicted	4th–5th c.	89%	15%
	11th–12th c.	11%	85%

Table 1: Confusion Matrix: Model Accuracy

Interpretability is a central concern for this research. Preliminary analysis of POS bigram frequencies (see Figure 1) reveals stable patterns for some sequences, such as pronoun–verb and adjective–verb, and clear diachronic

shifts for others. For example, verb–conjunction appears slightly more frequent in earlier centuries, while noun–noun and noun–adjective combinations increase markedly in later periods. These observations provide initial hypotheses about structural tendencies in Latin across time. They also highlight the potential of computational approaches to complement traditional philological methods by offering quantitative evidence of linguistic change.

Figure 1: Frequency of Selected POS Bigrams

This prototype represents a first step toward a more comprehensive model of diachronic variation in Latin. It demonstrates that even a relatively simple approach, based on syntactic features and binary classification, can achieve strong performance and reveal meaningful linguistic patterns. However, the scope of this initial model is deliberately limited: it focuses on two distant chronological windows and relies exclusively on part-of-speech bigrams. Future iterations will build on these foundations by incorporating additional linguistic dimensions, such as lexical, morphological, and semantic features, and by moving beyond binary classification toward finer-grained chronological resolution, ideally at the level of individual centuries. These developments will not only improve predictive accuracy but also deepen our understanding of the mechanisms underlying linguistic change. Throughout this process, interpretability will remain a central priority, ensuring that computational

results can be meaningfully integrated into philological and historical research.

In sum, this prototype provides preliminary evidence that the automatic dating of Latin texts is both technically feasible and promising as a tool for historical linguistics. While far from definitive, the results suggest that interpretable features can support accurate classification while remaining transparent enough for linguistic interpretation. The findings underscore the potential of computational methods to shed light on diachronic variation in Latin, complementing traditional scholarship with quantitative insights. Ultimately, this work contributes to a broader understanding of how language evolves over time.

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